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THE CONCEPTUALIZATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGY

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N. Meshko, M. Nikolaev. The conceptualization of the international digital marketing strategy. In this article authors examine the concept of the international digital marketing strategy and propose the refined definition of marketing strategy, as well as develop the definition of the international digital marketing strategy. The relevance of the work lies in the fact that in world, over time, information technologies of different levels are used more actively in all spheres of the socio-economic space and in order to be competitive companies need to understand the base concept of the international digital marketing strategy. In-depth analysis of classification of digital marketing strategies has been conducted. The key factors affecting international digital marketing strategy have been identified.

Keywords: international digital marketing strategy. Internet marketing, digital marketing, e-business, e-business models

In modern society, the Internet environment is objectively gaining momentum for marketing purposes. This channel of information and communication is characterized by an exceptional level of trust from users and has extremely high media resonance events.

Economic history and evolution of marketing demonstrate an urgent need for special attention to details, to methodological purity and soundness of the basis of the latest promising and universal solutions, numerous variants of which, in particular, are intensively generated in the field of Internet marketing today. Their critical review does not deny effective implementation, but can prevent unwanted and large-scale losses [2].

Analysis of recent research and publications and allocation of previously unresolved issues

Recently different aspects of international digital (or Internet) marketing strategy have received widespread attention. Quelch and Kilen (1996) [6], Hamil and Gregory (1997) [7], D. Hoffman et al. (1999) [8], Avlonitis and Karayanni (2000) [5], Porter (2001) [9] and Dale (2002) [10] conducted in-depth studies to understand those factors which are necessary to enhance business to business international Internet marketing implementation.

In 2004 researchers from the UK Riyad Eid and Myfanwy Trueman [11] provided a comprehensive empirical study of UK companies by exploring the factors affecting the success of business-to-business international Internet marketing (B-to-B IIM). They stated that B-to-B IIM is one of the key drivers in sustaining an organisation's competitive advantage.

In spite of a great number of scientific works related to Internet marketing and international strategy of digital development there is a lack of solid researches devoted to the conceptualization of an international digital marketing strategy.

The aim of the article is to perform comprehensive analysis of current stage of international digital marketing strategy development and provide the definition of its concept from scientific point of view.

The main part

Modern changes in media field change the "rules" of marketing. The traditional algorithm of payment for advertising based on the airtime or the frequency of contacts with the audience should be revised, because the transition from mass broadcasting to digital individualized media. The majority of digital, interactive media, involving the viewer himself and the potentially viral dissemination of information should change the approaches to marketing in general and marketing communications in particular. While the basic principles of marketing – positioning and segmentation – remain unchanged, digital channels create new ways and increase the speed of consumer engagement. Natural selection forces marketing to evolve, because consumers prefer those brands, which are more likely to develop digital channels.

The digital marketing strategy is a statement about how to achieve a context-specific marketing goal and determines solutions and directions regarding variables such as segmentation of the Internet market, definition of the target Internet market, positioning, Internet marketing complex, costs and performance evaluation in a rapidly changing Internet environment.

Thus, we emphasize that the extremely high variability of the Internet marketing environment is a serious problem for the development and subsequent implementation of the digital marketing strategy. The main contradiction is an achievement of a long-term competitive advantage in a rapidly changing Internet environment.

This forces most Internet companies create flexible business processes, management systems or develop unique resource systems and marketing strategies, which are difficult for competitors to reproduce. This causes, on the one hand, that a large

number of new companies are entering the Internet markets and, on the other hand, many of them go bankrupt or receive negative profits from commercial activities. The final comparison of the characteristics of the digital marketing strategy vs. the traditional marketing strategy is given in table below.

Table 1. Comparison of characteristics of the "Digital marketing strategy" vs "Traditional marketing strategy"

Criterion	Digital marketing strategy	Marketing strategy
Environment	the Internet	traditional
The speed of change of environmental factors	high	often low
Degree of formalization	often low	often high
Frequency of changes	high	low
Initiators of new strategies	low and middle levels of management	top and middle level managers

Source: Compiled by the authors on the materials [4]

The remaining criteria are identical for the majority to those that describe the differences between Internet marketing and traditional marketing, represented in the work of D. Strauss and R. Frost [11].

Types of Digital Marketing Strategies

Analysis of domestic and foreign authors' contributions showed the presence of a large number of types of Internet marketing strategies. In some cases, they are similar to traditional marketing strategies, but there are some peculiarities. For example, individual authors use the concept of Internet marketing model or e-business to determine the Internet marketing strategy.

D. Strauss and R. Frost consider the digital marketing strategy and the e-business model as equivalent concepts [11]. The authors understand the e-business model as a business method that contributes to profitability of a company by increasing revenues or reducing costs. In their opinion, the model of e-business requires the determination of value for the consumer [11]. In general, this criterion is fundamental in shaping digital marketing strategies in the context of the transfer of control from the seller to the consumer.

Thus, the authors believe that in conditions of maximum control from buyers, a prerequisite for a development of the digital marketing strategy should be offering value to a consumer, which is defined by the formula:

$$\text{VALUE} = \text{BENEFITS} - \text{COSTS} \quad (1)$$

The value, according to the authors, includes the consumer's perception of the benefits of the product / service: product characteristics, brand, supporting services, etc. The cost of purchasing a product / service includes expenses in monetary terms, time and effort, and emotional costs for customers.

Table 2. Classification of digital marketing strategies based on D. Strauss and R. Frost research

Elements of the marketing mix	Internet marketing strategies (e-business models)
Product	new products or services in digital form
Price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - price reduction through e-marketing - negotiation - segmented pricing
Distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - provision of advertising space on the site - direct sales online - information provider (marketing firms selling research online) - intermediaries online: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - brokers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - online exchange (exchange) - online auction - agents: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sales agent (one supplier) - agent manufacturers (more than one supplier) - event (specialized) portals - online shopping center - buying agents - auction for price reduction - consumer cooperatives - retailers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - digital merchants - traders of traditional goods
Marketing communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet advertising - promotion on the Internet - content offer - Email
Relationship marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - customer relationship management - community building

Source: Compiled by the authors on the materials [4]

The perception of the value is determined by beliefs, attitudes and experiences of consumers regarding the product / service. So, they are the ways to deliver value to customers through electronic communications [11]. The authors have proposed the following types of digital marketing strategies (electronic business models) (table below).

In October 2014 Gail Horwood [1], the vice president of digital strategy in Johnson & Johnson’s, described necessity for international company to have a global digital marketing strategy:

"...we had hundreds of different websites and digital platforms that we were operating upon globally. If you want to get a message across globally on your owned assets, you need to do that in the same way across the world".

So, as was said, Johnson & Johnson’s made a strategic decision to agree to "build certain types of things, with a website on a shared platform at the center". This work involved both internal and external vendors globally to build an open-source model.

The importance of international digital marketing strategy is confirmed by the experience of other multinational corporations (Coca Cola, Apple, Hilton, etc.).

Following the logic and proceeding from the above definitions of the digital marketing specifics, we can approach the definition of the international digital marketing strategy as configuration of a tailored value chain -the series of international activities required to produce and deliver a product or service – that enables a company to offer unique value using digital means and Internet space.

The challenge for organizations today is to understand the factors that play a critical role in utilizing Internet capabilities and their implications on business strategic objectives to enable them to compete successfully in the electronic age (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Factors affecting international digital marketing strategy
 Source: Own elaboration

An effective international digital marketing strategy involves the building of a global brand in the digital environment. Internet branding is a complex process, and today it is more effective than traditional. The main advantage is that branding in real space is limited by physical parameters, temporal and geographic boundaries, and in the virtual world this is not taken into account, branding is limited only by means of communication with the user.

D. Schulz and F. Kitchen [12], who developed the classification of a market place and its main characteristics depending on the stages of marketing evolution, defined the concept of an "interactive market place", which is associated with the development and commercialization of the Internet. In their opinion, with which one can agree, there is a transition of market power into the hands of consumers due to a new level of access to market information on products and services.

Assessing the qualitative shifts in the evolution of the market place according to the degree of ownership of market actors, they identified the most important ones, calling them "global building blocks" (fig 2):

Fig. 2. Global building blocks

Source: Compiled by the authors on the materials [12]

The development of these blogs has resulted in the formation of a global market place with a further consolidation of the buyer's dominant position in all four blocks.

Research shows that e-commerce creates new competitive advantages that combine the benefits of leadership, cost, technology and diversification strategies. Those who manage to use them receive not only additional surplus value, but also the maximum monopoly profit. Particular importance in these technologies is dedicated to the accumulation of commercial, scientific, technical and financial information, which becomes not only a commodity, but also the key to the company's financial success in the market. Such technologies are mostly accessible to diversify (especially vertically) global TNCs, which actively use computers and electronic networks in their activities that control or own electronic media. Such TNCs can choose the right asset, which determines, as we know, the nature of cash flow, to effectively use operational and financial leverage in the implementation of their financial strategies.

New types of marketing such as mobile, viral, guerrilla (provocative) or buzz marketing and blog marketing are primarily associated with the implementation of the concept of digital marketing. Recent studies show that the proportion of people using the Internet for entertainment is gradually falling. People are increasingly using the network for utilitarian purposes – search for goods, for example. At the same time, the computer games industry is flourishing, and marketers view it as a business and advertising platform for influencing a certain audience. Thus, it is estimated that today the rate of development of the game industry in the world exceeds television, film and music industry and reaches \$ 25 billion.

Conclusions

The concept of international digital marketing is basis for global competitiveness business strategy in today's market. The extremely high variability of the Internet marketing environment is a serious problem for the development and subsequent implementation of the digital marketing strategy.

We determine the international digital marketing strategy as configuration of a tailored value chain – the series of international activities required to produce and deliver a product or service – that enables a company to offer unique value using digital means and Internet space.

An effective international digital marketing strategy involves building of a global brand in the digital environment. In Internet marketing, the maximum success of brand development can be achieved using its basic elements, which are the foundation of the entire promotion strategy in combination with new tools: media and content advertising and search engine optimization. Comprehensive and well-considered application of all necessary means will ensure substantial brand promotion on the world wide web.

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